

Case for importance

Understanding the impacts
of technology adoption on
'good work'

Putting people first

Contents

Introduction	4
Context	7
The evidence	9
1 Access	11
2 Fair pay	12
3 Fair conditions	13
4 Equality	14
5 Dignity	15
6 Autonomy	16
7 Wellbeing	17
8 Support	18
9 Participation	19
10 Learning	20
Conclusion	21
Endnotes	23

Authors

Dr Abigail Gilbert
Dr Bertha Rohenkohl
Dr Matthew Hall
Gwendolin Barnard
Dr Umar Bodo
Professor James Hayton

With thanks to

Dr Vicente Silva
Dr Jonny C Clarke
Anna Thomas
Dora Meredith
Hannah Kitcher
Samuel Atwell
Hayfa Mohdzaini and
Ben Wilmott of the CIPD,
and Douglas White and
previously Gail Irvine of
Carnegie UK for their
helpful feedback.

This work has been produced
in partnership with the CIPD,
and funded by Carnegie UK.
The CIPD has produced an
[accompanying guide](#) to
responsible investment in
technology.

Published
May 2022

“

A focus on ‘good work’
will improve economic,
social and health
outcomes together.

Professor Sir Chris Pissarides
Institute for the Future of Work Co-Founder and Co-Chair

Introduction

Deriving benefits from technology adoption, for businesses and workers, is in large part dependent on approaches to design and deployment.¹ There is growing evidence that new technologies could have significant social and material impacts on work, job quality and ultimately wider society.

Technology² is often assumed to de facto improve productivity, and remove 'dirty, dull and dangerous' work from our societies.³ But this is not necessarily the reality. Despite increasing digitalisation, productivity growth has sharply declined across OECD countries over the past decades.⁴ It is down to how businesses make decisions about the way they adopt technology that will determine wider impacts.

This report demonstrates that there is a business case for taking a responsible approach to the adoption of technology in the workplace. It also demonstrates that there are moral, social and economic imperatives to prioritising 'good work', which will see returns at the level of individual, firm and society.

This report therefore makes the case for ensuring that the design and deployment of technology in the workplace considers impacts on all principles of 'good work'

as set out in the Institute for the Future of Work's Good Work Charter.⁵

The Good Work Charter

The Good Work Charter provides an organising framework to enable aspiration, alignment and action by different actors to shape a future of 'good work'. It sets out ten fundamental principles of 'good work' – work that promotes dignity, autonomy and equality; work that has fair pay and conditions; work where people are properly supported to develop their talents and have a sense of community.

The ten principles incorporate rights, freedoms and obligations relevant to work and the key institutions, ideas and conditions that shape work and experience of work. The Charter helps firms understand impacts on work and work quality, demonstrate compliance with the law in light of these impacts, and improve practice in key areas.

Good Work Charter

- 1 Access**
Everyone should have access to 'good work'

- 2 Fair pay**
Everyone should be fairly paid

- 3 Fair conditions**
Everyone should work on fair conditions set out on fair terms

- 4 Equality**
Everyone should be treated equally and without discrimination

- 5 Dignity**
Work should promote dignity

- 6 Autonomy**
Work should promote autonomy

- 7 Wellbeing**
Work should promote physical and mental wellbeing

- 8 Support**
Everyone should have access to institutions and people who can represent their interests

- 9 Participation**
Everyone should be able to take part in determining and improving working conditions

- 10 Learning**
Everyone should have access to lifelong learning and career guidance

Approaches to technology adoption

We identify a spectrum between 'high-road' and 'low-road' approaches to technology adoption.⁶

The 'high-road' approach centres human experience and contribution in the deployment of technology in the workplace, to create and maintain good quality work.⁷ This maximises the opportunities and minimises risks in the adoption of technology to produce optimal outcomes for people, firms and society as a whole. In particular, this can mean that technology supports worker wellbeing, alongside greater business productivity.

The 'low-road' approach does not properly consider human impacts or experience, and focuses on expected short-term economic gains.

This report uses the Good Work Charter to organise information about the benefits of a 'high-road' approach to technology adoption, and expose the risks, costs and impacts for businesses of taking a 'low-road' approach.

The Charter aims to encourage dynamic, values-based practice and policy-orientation as businesses introduce new technologies,⁸ and acts as a 'checklist' of the impacts of the introduction of new technology on work and job quality.⁹

Context

Context

The impact of technology on work

The world of work is going through one of the greatest technological transformations since industrialisation, variously called the 'rise of the robots,' 'the second machine age' or the 'fourth industrial revolution'.¹⁰ There is a growing consensus that this technological change is driving and/or exacerbating some economic trends,¹¹ and presents a specific set of risks.¹²

Conventionally, technology adoption at work is understood as the use of technology to replace human labour, and so displace workers. However, our research suggests that the impacts of technology adoption are more varied, and fall into six categories (see figure 1).

Figure 1: The impacts of automation

The impacts of automation on work:

1. Substitution – technology performs new tasks previously undertaken by workers. Example: A stock-monitoring system directly displaces the work of stock-room managers.

2. Transference – technology transfers tasks from the worker to others. Example: Workers use the HR information system self-service function to book annual leave instead of HR doing it for them.

3. Telepresence – technology reduces the need for physical proximity, enabling workers to perform tasks from any location. Example: Managers use monitoring software to check how much time people spend on non-work-related websites during working hours.

4. Creation – technology creates new tasks and even new jobs for people. Example: Engaging with stakeholders on social media on behalf of organisations has created demand for social media managers.

5. Augmentation – augmenting workers' capabilities. Example: Using a business intelligence tool augments a worker's ability to gain insights and run reports.

6. Intensification – doing more tasks in the allocated time. Example: A call centre worker uses online chat to talk to several customers at the same time.

These transformations alter ecosystems of accountability,¹³ and responsibility for job quality, which businesses must consider.

A single technological system can have all or many of these impacts simultaneously, for different parts of the workforce. A technology introduced to substitute for one role (for instance, a manager with a platform which schedules work and measures and monitors performance) can lead to changed outcomes for another (e.g. intensification). Technology adoption should therefore be understood and examined in the broad context of its implementation.

The evidence

The evidence

This section goes through the ten principles set out in the Good Work Charter, and presents evidence for the business benefits of a 'high-road' approach, and the possible harms and impacts of a 'low-road' approach.

A 'high-road' approach

This centres people in the process of technological adoption and recognises their contribution to productivity. A 'high-road' approach values 'good work' practices which support worker wellbeing, and are shown to improve worker productivity.¹⁴

A 'low-road' approach

This can generate poor quality work, which is strongly correlated with low worker productivity as well as wider individual and society-level harms. As worker wellbeing is secured by 'good work', and in turn contributes to business productivity, this creates a virtuous cycle.

A 'high-road' approach is increasingly critical as our contemporary approach to technology deployment is failing to secure productivity returns¹⁵ potentially because they are failing to give appropriate regard to the human contribution in value creation.¹⁶

Access

Everyone should have access to 'good work'

Taking the 'high road'

Benefits

Access to work builds resilience against health and economic shocks and underpins the other principles of 'good work'.¹⁷ The rights to work and access to decent work, freely given, have also been conceived as a fundamental right,¹⁸ given they are preconditions of other fundamental rights, and a life with dignity.¹⁹ Technology can support wider access to work – allowing workers to engage in opportunities at a distance, while also allowing employers to tap into a bigger talent pool. This helps to reduce information asymmetries in what work is available, and to support recruitment for roles which require rare skillsets. It also helps to connect workers to dynamic growth hubs, and widen access to work for communities with poorer access to the labour market.

The substitution of work can have impacts on access to work. It has obvious business benefits if employees are supported to continue in work with the introduction of new technologies through helping to build loyalty and engagement. In contrast, the data suggests that after layoffs the majority of companies suffer declines in profitability, and this decline may persist for years.²⁰ When workers who are retained see their long-time peers being dismissed, or not given the opportunity to retrain or reskill, it is likely that they feel demoralised and become less engaged with the company.

Taking the 'low road'

Risks

There are economic, social and political consequences of changed access to work. Increasingly as telepresence allows labour to be recruited from a distance, there are risks of contractual distancing, which could alter landscapes of opportunity and drive down wages.²¹

Poor access to 'good work' can also impact the wider family,²² lowering the educational attainment and wellbeing of children,²³ which can also have impacts at a community level.²⁴ Transition to unemployment is associated with increased risk of limiting illness in the following year, and involuntary income loss has varied negative health impacts.²⁵ First episodes of unemployment have less impact than subsequent ones²⁶ with risk of stroke and myocardial infarction doubled for those who are unemployed for a second time in a decade following unemployment,²⁷ as supported by studies which control for pre-existing health status.²⁸ Involuntary worklessness is linked to financial exclusion and poverty, cardiovascular mortality, suicide risk, higher rates of smoking and alcohol excess and a lack of control and autonomy that exacerbates poor mental and physical health.²⁹ Unemployment is associated with significant increases in the risk of hypertension and type-2 diabetes mellitus, among others.³⁰

Research suggests that downsizing a workforce by 1% leads to a 31% increase in voluntary turnover the next year.³¹ Further research³² suggests that after a layoff, survivors experience significantly lower job satisfaction (41%), lower organisational commitment (36%) and a decline in job performance (20%).³³

A recent study suggested those who are fearful of losing their job within the next 12 months can actually deliver increased productivity. However, given the known negative impacts of insecurity on worker wellbeing,³⁴ productivity at the expense of wellbeing is unlikely to be sustained at firm-level,³⁵ or for individuals.

Fair pay

Everyone should be fairly paid

Taking the 'high road'

Benefits

There is strong evidence that pay and benefits positively correlate with productivity.³⁶ Absolute pay, i.e. the take-home earnings, and relative pay, i.e. a worker's pay relative to a referent other, both impact productivity and health.

The effect of pay on productivity and job satisfaction is perhaps mostly reflected through relative pay, when workers compare their pay with others within the same company (internal equity) or with outsiders (external equity). Comparisons with others can lead to perceptions of injustice, which can have negative consequences on job performance.³⁷

Various studies argue that a good wage is quintessential for worker wellbeing, and productivity.³⁸⁻⁴³ Socio-economic status, which can be taken as a proxy for pay, is also a significant predictor of healthy life expectancy.⁴⁴

When businesses adopt new technologies in order to drive profits and productivity, the human contribution to subsequent value generation should be properly recognised in the form of fair pay. Companies who share the returns of development via profit sharing, have seen productivity increases of between 3.5 and 5%, with larger effects found for smaller organisations.⁴⁵

Profit sharing is also positively associated with innovation.⁴⁶ Approaches which combine employee empowerment and economic participation tend to have stronger positive impacts on performance, simultaneously reducing employee turnover, increasing employee intent to stay and increasing return on equity.^{47,48} However, the evidence on incentivisation is mixed.⁴⁹ Economic participation is shown to have positive benefits for employee wealth and wellbeing.^{50,51} Evidence also suggests that profit sharing and equity compensation increase employee satisfaction over and above the effects of higher pay.⁵²

Taking the 'low road'

Risks

Research has found that some firms may use insights from predictive analytics in the hiring process, and through management, to reduce remuneration of workers.⁵³ Further, technology which displaces labour is suggested to be a contributing factor in 'polarisation' whereby jobs in the middle of the pay range are devalued, or lost from the labour market,^{54,55} driving former middle-salary workers to also compete for those positions.⁵⁶ Economists have also identified a tendency towards 'capital-biased technological change' – whereby the returns of technology adoption see lower and lower shares returned to labour.⁵⁷

Determining fairness of pay as estimated through processes of technology adoption is challenging, as discussed in the Learning section below. Business models harnessing AI can also make the human contribution to value creation 'strategically invisible'⁵⁸ undermining negotiations around fair pay. Many 'superstar' platform businesses, to which many businesses now look for inspiration,⁵⁹ rely on low-wage work, and are underpinned by models of employment which are legally contested,⁶⁰ and or directly exploitative.⁶¹

Fair conditions

Everyone should work on fair conditions set out on fair terms

Taking the 'high road'

Benefits

Understanding the terms and conditions of work performance, and clear guidance and management around how to do well is core to achieving a sense of effort-reward balance within work.⁶² Research suggests that where workers feel a sense of effort-reward fairness, they deliver more innovative work, and have greater work ability.^{63,64} This also has positive impacts on wellbeing.⁶⁵

Worker ability to control the scheduling of work – a condition of work which is steadily decreasing in parts of the UK labour market, enabled by technology adoption and predictive scheduling⁶⁶ – is linked to a reduction in sickness absence, in turn improving performance.⁶⁷ Those working in favourable employment conditions are also four times less likely to develop limiting illness.⁶⁸ Clear opportunities to progress at work are key to fair conditions.

Taking the 'low road'

Risks

The use of algorithmic systems to tightly define and predict demand for work, in order to match it with supply of labour is increasingly common across sectors, and associated with a transformation of contract type.⁶⁹ Such contract changes can be used to reduce direct spend on labour, but also avoid the legal demands on employers to provide a safe working environment.^{70,71}

Technology has been associated with a polarisation of hours in work, with an increased tendency towards some overworking and others underworking.⁷² This exacerbates income inequality and changes the experience of work. It also determines who can participate in different jobs. A core condition of 'good work' is work-life balance, which can involve over-employment – or its inverse – underemployment.⁷³ Technological change is driving inequalities in access to hours of work. One thesis identified that declines in hours per worker were far higher in routine, manual jobs.⁷⁴ The study found that as 'high-skilled' workers increase their fraction of employment and work, 'medium-skilled' workers saw a decline in the share of employment, and a decline in hours per worker. 'Low-skilled' workers saw a substantial decrease in hours per worker. In turn, inequality in hours of work is entrenching polarisation of the labour market. This increasingly necessitates multiple jobs for some workers, which is associated with sleep disturbance and an increase in accidents inside and outside of work.^{75,76} Increased insecurity of work has been associated with increased risk of coronary artery disease and depression,^{77,78} and presents similar threats to health as unemployment.⁷⁹

Equality

Everyone should be treated equally and without discrimination

Taking the 'high road'

Benefits

Technology has the ability to improve equality within society, both at the individual level, by enabling individuals to participate in work where they would not otherwise be able to, and at the societal level by changing what work needs to be done, and creating moments to discuss how human work is valued.

Different people face different barriers when accessing work, demonstrating the need for flexibility at a firm and systems level to help individuals fulfil their potential. As much as two fifths of productivity growth since 1960 is the result of reducing barriers to work for women and Black, Asian and minority ethnic men.⁸⁰

Promoting equality at work has also been linked to diversifying, and quadrupling the total number of inventors.⁸¹

While not often designed to serve these objectives, technology can be deployed to increase diversity of the workforce, and to support dignity in work and equality in the workplace.⁸² Technology can improve productivity and performance, both in terms of including those with a disability⁸³ (at present only around half of all disabled people are in work)⁸⁴ and age inclusiveness.⁸⁵

The evidence on remote working (telepresence) and equalities is mixed. There is evidence to suggest telepresence can help enable caregivers to participate in work but this does not necessarily support 'good work',⁸⁶ and can create new challenges to inclusion.⁸⁷ Further in the long run there may be negative impacts on engagement.⁸⁸ Various studies suggest a decline in mental health which has knock-on effects for productivity.⁸⁹

Auditing of algorithmic systems used in hiring and recruitment, or workforce management, can highlight issues of systemic discrimination and social inequality which may otherwise go undetected.

Taking the 'low road'

Risks

The introduction of technology in the workplace can exacerbate existing economic inequalities, if risks are not well managed.⁹⁰ As professions are gendered, racialised and age biased, forms of technology adoption which substitute human labour can have different impacts on different parts of the workforce.⁹¹

The impact on displaced workers will also depend on whether they have the opportunity and support to transition to other jobs. Workers in high-risk occupations have on average 26% fewer desirable transitions compared to workers in lower-risk occupations.⁹²

Transference of performance review to consumers – for instance, call centre workers being evaluated on the length of time people hold the call – can drive and exacerbate discrimination without adequate mechanisms for redress.⁹³ Research has found that in the adoption of data-driven technologies for HR functions, across hiring recruitment and workforce management, can incur significant equality harms. While there was a time when data-driven systems were considered to be more fair than people, this 'myth' has now largely been dispelled.⁹⁴ This owes to recognition that data encodes the inequalities of history. Even when accurately predicting human behaviour, (e.g. the likelihood of women clicking to apply for senior leadership roles) making decisions on this basis (not showing women adverts for senior leadership roles) can cement the inequalities of history.

Bias is not the only challenge. There is also a lack of transparency about how hiring decisions are reached in AI reviewed applicants or workers.^{95,96} While statistical auditing tools can reveal important equality discrepancies, they are not an adequate solution to this challenge, and cannot guarantee compliance with UK law.⁹⁷ It is recommended that combined technical, and participatory auditing is used by organisations to help navigate this.⁹⁸

Dignity

Work should promote dignity

Taking the 'high road'

Benefits

Promoting the dignity of workers has been found to support more expansive leadership than conventional human-resource management approaches.⁹⁹ All human beings are inherently worthy of respect and protection of their psychological, moral and physical integrity.¹⁰⁰ Work to promote dignity as technology is introduced could be perceived as that which promotes wellbeing and equality.¹⁰¹

However, more expansive conceptions also consider the role of self-worth and sense of self, rights to develop one's personality and form relationships with others.¹⁰² Our self-respect depends critically on how others treat us, particularly those we see on a regular basis. Work is the space in which most people spend most of their time and therefore relationships at work strongly contribute to self-concept.

Research has found that the introduction of technology can lead people to feel less valued, by both their employer and by society as a whole.¹⁰³ Working to build organisational cultures which promote the dignity of workers involves abiding to all other 'good work' principles, in particular autonomy and participation.

Taking the 'low road'

Risks

There are risks of the intensification of both desk based,¹⁰⁴ and frontline work under algorithmic management.¹⁰⁵ This can drive workers to engage in activities which diminish their dignity.¹⁰⁶

Data-driven systems substituting human work of recognition can also dehumanise workers through failing to appropriately recognise their humanity.¹⁰⁷ By reducing opportunities for dialogue between workers, and surveilling communications between workers, data-driven systems can also curtail freedom of expression.¹⁰⁸ Beyond undermining the 'good work' principle of 'support', this can also be seen to undermine 'free development of personality'.¹⁰⁹ Notably, the CAHAI guidance highlights risk of instrumentalisation in which an individual is treated as exchangeable, and the risk of psychological 'chilling' effects on behaviour. The guidance highlights that humans' sense of dignity and life quality should be enhanced by technology, rather than diminished.¹¹⁰

Autonomy

Work should promote autonomy

Taking the 'high road'

Benefits

Jobs that have high autonomy and task feedback tend to be most strongly related to pay satisfaction, which positively correlates with productivity.¹¹¹ However, when pay satisfaction, voice and autonomy are disaggregated for their impact on satisfaction with work, voice and autonomy play a much larger role than wage in explaining satisfaction with work. Autonomy can also drive efficiency, and the motivation of workers within firms.¹¹² Employee-owned businesses in the UK, especially small- and medium-sized businesses, are proportionately more profitable than their non-employee owned counterparts.¹¹³ This trend is associated with the fact employee-owned firms tend to grant more autonomy in decision making to their employees. Employee-owned businesses also grow faster in terms of employment and are more resilient over business cycles.¹¹⁴ This resilience effect is reinforced by greater stability of the workforce and organisational ability to adapt to change.¹¹⁵

Taking the 'low road'

Risks

Poorly designed, the introduction of technology in the workplace can delimit skill use and autonomy, reducing discretion over what tasks constitute work, and in turn, workers' ability to define value within a firm.¹¹⁶

Use of technology to reduce autonomy can also intensify work, and drive unhealthy environments of self-discipline if wider conditions to protect and promote worker wellbeing are not in place.¹¹⁷ Evidence suggests that autonomy can decline for both high- and low-skill workers through routinisation, reducing professional discretion.¹¹⁸

Questions have also been raised around 'manipulation' by AI.¹¹⁹ Employers should consider the proportionality of technological deployments designed to increase productivity, relative to the autonomy of workers. Developing wristbands to guide workers' hands,¹²⁰ or tracking their eye movements to evaluate tiredness,¹²¹ significantly diminishes the agency of the worker and introduce significant ethical questions. There is increasing evidence that technology is designed and deployed to intensify work, referred to as 'effort-biased' technological change,¹²² is associated with a reduction in autonomy. Such a reduction in autonomy can impact the effort-reward balance of work,¹²³ which is closely linked to wellbeing.

This is something businesses must be cognisant of, as evidence suggests that narratives of technological progress can lead employers to forget and overlook the lived experience of surveillance technology.¹²⁴ Further, the use of what has been described as 'hyper-nudge'¹²⁵ techniques within software applications, which give an illusion of choice within a constrained decision making environment, present ethical challenges.

6

Wellbeing

Work should promote physical and mental wellbeing

Taking the 'high road'

Benefits

Worker wellbeing is an outcome of taking a 'high-road' approach in line with all 'good work' principles, as demonstrated throughout this report.

It is a legal responsibility for firms to protect physical and mental health. Several have argued that promoting wellbeing and human flourishing at work is the fundamental purpose of an economy.¹²⁶ Worker wellbeing is underpinned by, and an outcome of access, terms and conditions, and fair pay.¹²⁷ Health, and in particular mental health, is also determined, by the social aspects of work – opportunities for learning, autonomy¹²⁸ and dignity shape job satisfaction, a precondition for the wellbeing and general life satisfaction of individuals.¹²⁹ People who feel well in themselves have been found to make more effort and show better performance.¹³⁰ Ultimately workers with higher levels of wellbeing are more productive over the long term.¹³¹

Approaches to work, and its redesign through technology adoption, which promote capabilities¹³² demonstrate great rewards. Increasingly employers are also supporting the workforce to use technology to monitor their own wellbeing. The extent to which this delivers benefits depends on implementation.¹³³

Taking the 'low road'

Risks

An aspiration for technology introduction has been the removal of 'dull, dirty and dangerous' work from the labour market, allowing the development of an economy which better supports human flourishing. However, research suggests some deployments can increase worker vulnerability to harm from work that damages wellbeing.¹³⁴ Data analytics have been, and are increasingly used to filter workers with poor mental health from the workforce,¹³⁵ entrenching inequalities.

Further, the link between digital technologies and intensification of work¹³⁶ has significant impacts on health. Excessive monitoring has psycho-social consequences including increased resistance, reduced job satisfaction, increased stress, decreased organisational commitment and increased turnover propensity.¹³⁷ While remote working was broadly conceived to promote wellbeing, there is evidence to suggest it introduced novel forms of 'techno-stress'.¹³⁸ Reviews suggest digital communication is taxing on workers.¹³⁹

Job demands and pressures, degree of autonomy and flexibility, quality of interactions with supervisors and coworkers, frequency of shift work, and length of the workday all determine worker wellbeing,¹⁴⁰ therefore when adopting new technologies in the workplace, it is important to consider the impacts across all of these dimensions.

Support

Everyone should have access to institutions and people who can represent their interests

Taking the 'high road'

Benefits

The principle of support incorporates rights to freedom of association and bargaining, which are linked to wider responsibilities to practice inclusivity. These point to the need to develop and maintain a supportive workplace culture. Many of the benefits associated with the introduction of technology are dependent on supportive working environments. Previous work suggests a correlation between supportive working environments and productivity.¹⁴¹ High-involvement approaches to management are supportive of the implementation of advanced technologies.¹⁴² Organisations obtain higher levels of productivity from investments in advanced information technologies when combined with more sophisticated management practices.¹⁴³

Some work suggests productivity returns from training are contingent on the simultaneous implementation of supportive management practices, such as employee participation, team-based work, and some element of reward contingent on organisational performance.¹⁴⁴ Evidence also indicates that there is more effective transfer of training where there is a more supportive work environment.¹⁴⁵

The most important source of workplace satisfaction, which drives productivity, is a worker's relationship with their manager.¹⁴⁶ As the development of organisations, aided by technology, sees workers increasingly fragmented,¹⁴⁷ unions can play a helpful role in mediation, enabling meaningful consultation and addressing information asymmetries.

Processes which engage workers in discussion about technological change, such as technology forums, have been advocated as a tool to mediate between workers and employers through disruption, modelling social partnership.¹⁴⁸ Deployed well, technology can support workers and their representatives to better understand work and conditions.¹⁴⁹

Taking the 'low road'

Risks

As a core source of relationships, access to work and supportive relationships within this environment can reduce loneliness, a known mortality risk.¹⁵⁰ At a more systemic level, work is part of the social infrastructure which connects people, contributing to social cohesion.¹⁵¹ The adoption of technology which reduces support and connection within a firm can hamper these benefits. Through the intensification of work, algorithmic systems have been found to delimit the extent to which workers are able to engage in dialogue with colleagues,¹⁵² which can be a core aspect of a positive working environment.

Data-driven systems can also be used to promote anti-union activities.¹⁵³ As well as constraining the opportunity for workers to have access to institutions that can represent their interests and uphold their wellbeing, anti-union activity may pose significant reputational risks to businesses. This is well exemplified by some business practices of union-blocking.¹⁵⁴

Participation

Everyone should be able to take part in determining and improving working conditions

Taking the 'high road'

Benefits

The UK Government promotes participation as a route to innovation in new civic technology.¹⁵⁵ The introduction of technology presents a unique challenge and opportunity for work redesign. It should therefore be taken as a key moment for workforce involvement in decision making to ensure work redesign benefits both workers and businesses. Empirical evidence has demonstrated that various forms of employee involvement can promote organisational performance,¹⁵⁶ and as shown by a comprehensive meta-analysis, productivity.¹⁵⁷ One study cites a 14% higher productivity rate where voice and representation is high.¹⁵⁸

The use of participative techniques, including involvement in decisions related to technology adoption, work organisation, and work design can help to reinforce investments supporting productivity returns from technology adoption.¹⁵⁹ Employee participation in decision making can also improve worker wellbeing by leading to more challenging and intrinsically rewarding work.¹⁶⁰

Participation can also drive higher levels of satisfaction with pay, autonomy and supportive environments, relative to workers in non-employee owned firms.¹⁶¹

Taking the 'low road'

Risks

It is increasingly common for algorithmic systems to be presented as neutral, and for such systems to be used to make important decisions about work. However, such systems cannot be neutral¹⁶² and if deployed poorly, can be used to foreclose debate about how work is managed, and about the inevitable trade-offs which arise in algorithmic decision making.¹⁶³

This is particularly critical as algorithmic systems can reduce opportunities for workers to have a voice, and create barriers to access to management.¹⁶⁴ Workers who are managed by platforms find it increasingly difficult to be represented in processes of decision making.¹⁶⁵ While the internet can support decentralisation of power, new research on the values encoded in machine-learning research and development suggests that the centralising of control is core to much design.¹⁶⁶

A growing body of work supports preemptive impact assessment, involving workers, before the introduction of any algorithmic system in practice. Because it is not possible for such systems to be neutral, it is essential that human dialogue accompanies the use of algorithmic systems in decision making about work. This could also take the form of regular, participatory auditing.¹⁶⁷

Learning

Everyone should have access to lifelong learning and career guidance

Taking the 'high road'

Benefits

Companies that re-train their workers for new roles within or outside the company have tended to benefit financially.¹⁶⁸ Retraining employees who have proven track records and potential can be about one-and-a-half to three times cheaper than hiring new talent.¹⁶⁹ A study by the Centre for Economic Performance reports that a one percentage point increase in training investment in an industry is associated with a 0.6% increase in value added per worker, and a 0.3% increase in wages.¹⁷⁰ Another finds a 0.7% increase in value added per employee.¹⁷¹ Given that the impact of training on productivity is actually twice that observed on wages, and that most research operationalises productivity in terms of wages, this means that prior work has significantly under-estimated the positive productivity effects of training.¹⁷²

There is also evidence that employee satisfaction with training is a significant predictor of overall job satisfaction, and therefore can be expected to be associated with job engagement, organisational commitment and reduced employee turnover, each of which is also supportive of productivity.^{173,174} One analysis found an increase in revenue of 32% after a firm chose to upskill and retain, rather than make redundant 100,000 workers.¹⁷⁵ Education also determines life expectancy.¹⁷⁶⁻¹⁷⁸

Taking the 'low road'

Risks

Pay differentials within firms are commonly understood to equate to different 'objective' levels of skill. As a result, the principles of 'fair pay' and 'learning' are often considered concurrently in processes of technological adoption, as skills requirements for roles change with the adoption of new technology.

The challenge in re-valuing work, and estimating changes in skills level following the introduction of new technology, is that what workers end up doing after technologies are introduced cannot always be foreseen.¹⁷⁹ In some cases, it can reduce opportunities for learning, expression of human skill, and capability.¹⁸⁰ While technology can store information and make it available for less-skilled workers to deliver the same outputs, increasing productivity, such processes – by taking information held in people (human capital), and codifying it (incorporating within capital) – can devalue labour. This in turn de-skills work for those who remain employed, working against the principle of learning.

Understanding these processes, and their implications for workers is critical to securing 'good work' through technological transition. Research shows that investment in people as technology is introduced can maximise use of the technology, and experience of work for staff. At present, workers with the least formal qualifications also receive the least investment in skills development by businesses.¹⁸¹ This can work against the long-term interests of the business, who may lose staff with strong organisational experience and knowledge, and can entrench inequality.

10

Conclusion

Conclusion

History teaches us that the question of who technology benefits depends on why and how it is adopted and designed. It also teaches us that the impacts of technological transformations are unevenly spread.

Failure to ensure that 'good work' principles are embedded into the process of adopting technology has negative consequences for worker wellbeing, with negative knock on effects for families,¹⁸² children,¹⁸³ and communities.¹⁸⁴ It also negatively impacts business, as poor quality work is linked to low productivity. Focusing on 'good work' through technology adoption ensures better lives for individuals, better and more sustainable outcomes for firms, and improved wider social outcomes.

Work is at the centre of people's lives. It is the thread that connects people's everyday experience with their community, the economy and the state, public policy and private ventures. The costs of taking a 'low-road' approach are borne by workers, employers and society.¹⁸⁵

This report indicates the benefits that society, public and private actors may be able to reap – including business productivity gains, democratic values and normative appropriateness – by following the 'high road' of socially responsible technology adoption at work.

To deliver the true potential of technology, principles of 'good work' must be made central to its design and deployment in workplaces.

Endnotes

Endnotes

- 1 Research has shown that there is a strong positive correlation between good will, profitability and long-term success. See: Wang, Yijing, and Guido Berens. 2015. “The Impact of Four Types of Corporate Social Performance on Reputation and Financial Performance”. *Journal of Business Ethics* 131 (2): 337–359. Available at: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10551-014-2280-y>
- 2 We define ‘technology’ broadly, to include artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML), the internet, the internet of things, big data analysis, digital technologies; combining and applying these technologies in diverse ways; and also the collection of techniques, skills, processes and knowledge used by humans in relation to these technologies’. Definition from the report of the Future of Work Commission. Available at: https://uploads-ssl.webflow.com/5f57d40eb1c2ef22d8a8ca7e/5f71a28418550428b77d4ab9_Future_of_Work_Commission_Report__December_2017.pdf
- 3 Takayama, Leila, Wendy Ju, and Clifford Nass. 2008. “Beyond dirty, dangerous and dull: what everyday people think robots should do.” In *2008 3rd ACM/IEEE International Conference on Human-Robot Interaction (HRI)* 25–32. IEEE. Available at: <http://www-cdr.stanford.edu/~wendyju/publications/hri114-takayama.pdf>
- 4 OECD. 2019. “Digitalisation and productivity: a story of complementarities.” Available at: <https://www.oecd.org/economy/growth/digitalisation-productivity-and-inclusiveness/>
- 5 The Good Work Charter provides a composite of principles and standards capturing the dimensions of good-quality and decent work. It incorporates fundamental legal, social and economic rights. Available at: <https://www.ifow.org/publications/the-ifow-good-work-charter>
- 6 Milkman, Ruth. 1998. “The new American workplace: high road or low road?.” In *Workplaces of the Future*, pp. 25–39. Palgrave, London.
- 7 Pasquale, Frank. 2020. *New Laws of Robotics: Defending Human Expertise in the Age of AI*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
- 8 See this in practice: EU-Nited. 2020. ‘Good Work Charter of the European Robotics Industry’. Available at: https://www.eu-nited.net/pdfs/robotics/good_work_charter/#1
- 9 Gilbert, Abigail and Anna Thomas. 2021. “An Amazonian Era: The Gigification of Work”. *Institute for the Future of Work*. Available at: <https://www.ifow.org/publications/the-amazonian-era-the-gigification-of-work>
- 10 Schwab, Klaus. 2016. *The Fourth Industrial Revolution*. London: Penguin.
- 11 Goos, Maarten, and Alan Manning. 2007. “Lousy and lovely jobs: The rising polarization of work in Britain.” *The review of economics and statistics* 89 (1): 118–133. Available at: http://eprints.lse.ac.uk/20002/1/Lousy_and_Lovely_Jobs_the_Rising_Polarization_of_Work_in_Britain.pdf
- 12 CIPD. 2019. *People and Machines: From Hype to Reality*. Available at: https://www.cipd.co.uk/Images/people-and-machines-exec-summary_tcm18-56971.pdf; Slaughter, Rebecca Kelly, Janice Kopec, and Mohamad Batal. 2020. “Algorithms and Economic Justice: A Taxonomy of Harms and a Path Forward for the Federal Trade Commission.” *Yale Journal of Law & Technology* 23: S1-S1. Available at: https://law.yale.edu/sites/default/files/area/center/isp/documents/algorithms_and_economic_justice_master_final.pdf
- 13 Birch, Kean, and D. T. Cochrane. 2021. “Big Tech: Four Emerging Forms of Digital Rentiership.” *Science as Culture* 1–15. Available at: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/09505431.2021.1932794>
- 14 Carnegie UK. 2020. “Can Good Work Solve the Productivity Puzzle?” Available at: <https://www.carnegieuktrust.org.uk/publications/can-good-work-solve-the-productivity-puzzle/>
- 15 Goodridge, Peter, Jonathan Haskel, and Gavin Wallis. 2018. “Accounting for the UK productivity puzzle: a decomposition and predictions.” *Economica* 85 (339): 581–605.
- 16 Newlands, Gemma. 2021 “Lifting the curtain: Strategic visibility of human labour in AI-as-a-Service.” *Big Data & Society* 8 (1): 205395172111016026.
- 17 Atwell, Sam et al. 2021. “The Good Work Monitor”. *Institute for the Future of Work*. Available at: <https://www.ifow.org/resources/the-good-work-monitor>
- 18 Hepple, Bob. 1981. “A right to work?” *Industrial Law Journal*. 10(2): 65–83. Available at: <https://academic.oup.com/ilj/article-abstract/10/1/65/766623>
- 19 Parker, Marty, Milica Bucknall, Carol Jagger, and Ross Wilkie. 2020. “Population-based estimates of healthy working life expectancy in England at age 50 years: analysis of data from the English Longitudinal Study of Ageing.” *Lancet Public Health* 5 (7): e395–e403. Available at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32619541/>
- 20 Datta, D.K., et al. 2010. “Causes and effects of employee downsizing: A review and synthesis”, *Journal of Management*. SAGE PublicationsSage CA: Los Angeles, CA. p. 281–348.
- 21 De Stefano, Valerio, Antonio Aloisi, Nicola Countouris. 2022. “The Metaverse is a Labour Issue” *Social Europe*. Available at: <https://socialeurope.eu/the-metaverse-is-a-labour-issue>
- 22 Bubonya, Melisa, Deborah A. Cobb-Clark, and Mark Wooden. 2014. “A family affair: job loss and the mental health of spouses and adolescents.” *Institute for the Study of Labor (IZA)*. Available at: <https://docs.iza.org/dp8588.pdf>

Endnotes

- 23 Brand, Jennie E. 2015. "The far-reaching impact of job loss and unemployment." *Annual Review of Sociology* 41: 359–375. Available at: <https://www.annualreviews.org/doi/abs/10.1146/annurev-soc-071913-043237>
- 24 Tcherneva, Pavlina R. 2017. "Unemployment: The silent epidemic." *Levy Economics Institute*, Working Papers Series 895. Available at: https://www.levyinstitute.org/pubs/wp_895.pdf
- 25 Naik, Yannish et al. 2017. "The macro-economic determinants of health and health inequalities—umbrella review protocol" *Systematic Reviews* 6 (222). Available at: <https://systematicreviewsjournal.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13643-017-0616-2>
- 26 Bartley, M., Sacker, A. & Clarke, P. 2004. "Employment status, employment conditions, and limiting illness: prospective evidence from the British household panel survey 1991–2001". *Journal Epidemiol Community Health*. 58(6): 501–506. Available at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/15143119/>
- 27 Gallo, William. T. et al. 2004. "Involuntary job loss as a risk factor for subsequent myocardial infarction and stroke: Findings from The Health and Retirement Survey". *Am. J. Ind. Med.* 45: 408–416. Available at: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC1351254/>
- 28 Schmitz, H. 2011. "Why are the unemployed in worse health? The causal effect of unemployment on health." *Labour Economics* 18(1): 71–78. Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0927537110000953>
- 29 The Association of Directors of Public Health. 2018. "Policy Position: Living and Working Well". Available at: <http://www.adph.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2018/05/ADPH-Position-Statement-Living-and-Working-Well-1.pdf>
- 30 Waynforth, David. 2018. "Unstable employment and health in middle age in the longitudinal 1970 British Birth Cohort Study". *Evol. Med. Public Health*. 92–99. Available at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29692897/>
- 31 Trevor, Charlie.O. and Anthony J. Nyberg. 2008. "Keeping Your Headcount When All about You Are Losing Theirs: Downsizing, Voluntary Turnover Rates, and the Moderating Role of HR Practices". *The Academy of Management Journal*. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/211395271_Keeping_Your_Headcount_When_All_About_You_Are_Losing_Theirs_Downsizing_Voluntary_Turnover_Rates_and_The_Moderating_Role_of_HR_Practices
- 32 Sverke, M., J. Hellgren, and K. Näswall. 2002., "No security: A meta-analysis and review of job insecurity and its consequences." *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 2002. 7: 242–264. Available at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/12148956/>
- 33 Sverke, Magnus, Johnny Hellgren, and Katharina Näswall. 2002. "No security: A meta-analysis and review of job insecurity and its consequences". *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*. 7: 242–264. Available at: <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2002-01632-005>
- 34 Parker, Marty, Milica Bucknall, Carol Jagger, and Ross Wilkie. 2020. "Population-based estimates of healthy working life expectancy in England at age 50 years: analysis of data from the English Longitudinal Study of Ageing." *The Lancet Public Health* 5(7): e395–e403. Available at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32619541/>
- 35 Warhust, Chris and Derek Bosworth. 2020. "Does Good Work Have a Positive Effect on Productivity? Developing the Evidence Base". In: *Can Good Work Solve the Productivity Puzzle? The RSA*. Available at: <https://www.thersa.org/globalassets/reports/2020/can-good-work-solve-the-productivity-puzzle.pdf>
- 36 Ibid.
- 37 Williams, M.L., M.A. McDaniel, and N.T.J.J.o.A.P. Nguyen. 2006. "A meta-analysis of the antecedents and consequences of pay level satisfaction" *Journal of Applied Psychology*. 91(2): 392. Available at: <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2006-03206-011>
- 38 Ton, Zeynep and Sarah Kalloch. 2017. "Transforming today's bad jobs into tomorrow's good jobs". *Harvard Business Review*. Available at: <https://hbr.org/2017/06/transforming-todays-bad-jobs-into-tomorrows-good-jobs>
- 39 Acemoglu, Daron. 2001. "Good jobs versus bad jobs". *Journal of Labor Economics*, 19(1): 1–21. Available at: https://www.journals.uchicago.edu/doi/abs/10.1086/209978?mod=article_inline&mobileUi=0
- 40 Rodrik, D. and C. Sabel. 2019. "Building a good jobs economy". *Harvard University*. Available at: <https://drodrik.scholar.harvard.edu/publications/building-good-jobs-economy>
- 41 Ton, Zeynep. 2014. *The Good Jobs Strategy: How the smartest companies invest in employees to lower costs and boost profits*. Houghton Mifflin Harcourt.
- 42 Ton, Zeynep. 2012. "Why "good jobs" are good for retailers". *Harvard Business Review*. 90(1-2): 124–31, 154. Available at: <https://hbr.org/2012/01/why-good-jobs-are-good-for-retailers>
- 43 Ton, Zeynep. 2017. "The Case for Good Jobs." *Harvard Business Review*. Available at: <https://hbr.org/2017/11/the-case-for-good-jobs>
- 44 Parker, Marty, Milica Bucknall, Carol Jagger, and Ross Wilkie. 2020. "Population-based estimates of healthy working life expectancy in England at age 50 years: analysis of data from the English Longitudinal Study of Ageing." *The Lancet Public Health* 5 (7): e395–e403. Available at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32619541/>
- 45 Kruse, Douglas L., Joseph R. Blasi, and Richard B. Freeman. 2012. "Does linking worker pay to firm performance help the best firms do even better?" *National Bureau of Economic Research (NBER) Working Paper* 17745. Available at: <https://www.nber.org/papers/w17745>

Endnotes

- 46 Aerts, Kris, Kornelius Kraft, and Julia Lang. 2013. "Profit-sharing and innovation". *Industrial and Corporate Change*. 24(6): 1377–1392.
Available at: <https://academic.oup.com/icc/article-abstract/24/6/1377/2357780>
- 47 Kruse, Douglas L., Joseph R. Blasi, and Richard B. Freeman. 2012. "Does linking worker pay to firm performance help the best firms do even better?" *National Bureau of Economic Research (NBER) Working Paper* 17745.
Available at: <https://www.nber.org/papers/w17745>
- 48 Blasi, Joseph, Richard Freeman and Douglas Kruse. 2016. "Do broad-based employee ownership, profit sharing and stock options help the best firms do even better?" *British Journal of Industrial Relations*. Mar;54(1): 55–82.
Available at: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/bjir.12135>
- 49 Kohn, Alfie. 1993. "Why Incentive Plans Cannot Work" *Harvard Business Review*.
Available at: <https://hbr.org/1993/09/why-incentive-plans-cannot-work>
- 50 Kruse, Douglas L., Joseph R. Blasi, and Richard B. Freeman. 2012. "Does linking worker pay to firm performance help the best firms do even better?" *National Bureau of Economic Research (NBER) Working Paper* 17745.
Available at: <https://www.nber.org/papers/w17745>
- 51 McQuaid, Ronald et al. 2012. "Fit for work? Health and Wellbeing of Employees in Employee Owned Business: Final Report to Employee Ownership Association". Employee Ownership Association.
Available at: https://www.academia.edu/4271350/Health_and_wellbeing_of_employees_in_employee_owned_businesses
- 52 Bryson, Alex. et al. 2016. "Share capitalism and worker wellbeing". *Labour Economics*. 42: 151–158.
Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0927537116301051>
- 53 Newman, Nathan. 2007. "Reengineering workplace bargaining: how big data drives lower wages and how reframing labor law can restore information equality in the workplace." *University of Cincinnati law review*. 85: 693.
Available at: https://search.lib.asu.edu/discovery/fulldisplay/cdi_gale_infotracacademiconefile_A542495682/01ASU_INST:01ASU
- 54 Salvatori, Andrea. 2015. "The anatomy of job polarisation in the UK." *Journal for labour market research* 52(1): 1–15.
Available at: <https://www.iza.org/publications/dp/9193/the-anatomy-of-job-polarisation-in-the-uk>
- 55 Goos, Maarten, and Alan Manning. 2003. "Lousy and lovely jobs: The rising polarization of work in Britain." *The review of economics and statistics* 89 (1): 118–133.
Available at: http://eprints.lse.ac.uk/20002/1/Lousy_and_Lovely_Jobs_the_Rising_Polarization_of_Work_in_Britain.pdf
- 56 Autor, David. 2007. "The polarisation of the US labour market: evidence, explanations and implications for higher education." Available at: <http://forum.mit.edu/articles/the-polarization-of-the-u-s-labor-market-evidence-explanations-and-implications-for-higher-education/>
- 57 Karabarbounis, Loukas and Brent Neiman. 2013. "The Global Decline of the Labour Share". *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 129(1), pp. 35–78.
Available at: <https://academic.oup.com/qje/article-abstract/129/1/61/1899422?redirectedFrom=fulltext>
- 58 Newlands, Gemma. 2021. "Lifting the curtain: Strategic visibility of human labour in AI-as-a-Service." *Big Data & Society* 8 (1). Available at: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/205395172111016026>
- 59 Nurvala, Juha-Pekka. 2015. "'Uberisation' is the future of the digitalised labour market." *European View* 14 (2): 231–239.
Available at: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1007/s12290-015-0378-y>
- 60 Dubal, Veena. 2019. "An Uber Ambivalence: Employee Status, Worker Perspectives, & Regulation in the Gig Economy." *UC Hastings Research Paper* 381. Available at: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3488009
- 61 Mellino, Emiliano, Charles Boutaud and Gareth Davies. 2021. "Deliveroo Riders can earn as little as £2 per hour during shifts". *The Bureau of Investigative Journalism*. <https://www.thebureauinvestigates.com/stories/2021-03-25/deliveroo-riders-earning-as-little-as-2-pounds#:~:text=Deliveroo%20pays%20per%20delivery%2C%20as,it%20rises%20to%20%C2%A38.20>
- 62 Siegrist, Johannes. 2016. "Effort-reward imbalance model." In *Stress: Concepts, cognition, emotion, and behavior*, pp. 81–86. Academic Press. Available at: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/9781118993811.ch2>
- 63 Janssen, Onne. 2000. "Job demands, perceptions of effort-reward fairness and innovative work behaviour." *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology* 73 (3): 287–302.
Available at: <https://bpspsychub.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1348/096317900167038>
- 64 Bethge, Matthias, Friedrich Michael Radoschewski, and Christoph Gutenbrunner. 2012. "Effort-reward imbalance and work ability: cross-sectional and longitudinal findings from the Second German Sociomedical Panel of Employees." *BMC public health* 12 (1) 1–9. Available at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/23067110/>
- 65 De Jonge, Jan, Hans Bosma, Richard Peter, and Johannes Siegrist. 2000. "Job strain, effort-reward imbalance and employee ell-being: a large-scale cross-sectional study." *Social science & medicine* 50 (9): 1317–1327.
Available at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/10728851/>
- 66 Algorithmic systems are increasingly used to measure, monitor and predict demand for tasks in UK businesses. See: Gilbert, Abigail and Anna Thomas. 2021. "The Amazonian Era: The gigification of work". *Institute for the Future of Work*. Available at: <https://www.ifow.org/publications/the-amazonian-era-the-gigification-of-work>

Endnotes

- 67 Ala-Mursula, Leena, Jussi Vahtera, Anne Linna, Jaana Pentti, and Mika Kivimäki. 2005. "Employee worktime control moderates the effects of job strain and effort-reward imbalance on sickness absence: the 10-town study." *Journal of Epidemiology & Community Health* 59 (10): 851-857. Available at: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC1732907/>
- 68 Bartley, Mel, Amanda Sacker, and Paul Clarke. 2004. "Employment status, employment conditions, and limiting illness: prospective evidence from the British household panel survey 1991-2001." *Journal of Epidemiology & Community Health* 58 (6): 501-506. Available at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/15143119/>
- 69 Gilbert, Abigail and Anna Thomas. 2021. "An Amazonian Era: The Gigification of Work." *Institute for the Future of Work*. Available at: <https://www.ifow.org/publications/the-amazonian-era-the-gigification-of-work>
- 70 Tran, Molly and Rosemary, K. Sokas. 2017. "The Gig Economy and Contingent Work: An Occupational Health Assessment." *J. Occup. Environ. Med.* 59(4), e63-e66. Available at: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5374746/>
- 71 Graham, M., Hjorth, I. & Lehdonvirta, V. 2017. "Digital labour and development: impacts of global digital labour platforms and the gig economy on worker livelihoods." *Transfer: European Review of Labour and Research*. 23: 135-162. Available at: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/1024258916687250>
- 72 Athene Laws, Helen. 2020. "Inequality in Labour Markets", PhD Submitted to the University of Cambridge. Available at: <https://www.repository.cam.ac.uk/handle/1810/301991>
- 73 Irvine, Gail, Douglas White and Mark Diffley. 2018. "Measuring Good Work: The Final Report of the Measuring Job Quality Group" Carnegie UK. Available at: <https://www.carnegieuktrust.org.uk/publications/measuring-good-work-the-final-report-of-the-measuring-job-quality-working-group/>
- 74 Laws, Athene Helen. 2020. *Inequality in Labour Markets (Doctoral thesis)*. University of Cambridge. Available at: <https://www.repository.cam.ac.uk/handle/1810/301991>
- 75 Marucci-Wellman, Helen R., Joanna L. Willetts, Tin-Chi Lin, Melan J. Brennan and Santosh K. Verma. 2014. "Work in multiple jobs and the risk of injury in the US working population." *Am. J. Public Health* 104(1): 134-42. Available at: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3910039/>
- 76 Marucci-Wellman, Helen R., David A. Lombardi and Joanna L. Willetts. 2016. "Working multiple jobs over a day or a week: Short-term effects on sleep duration." *Chronobiol. Int.* 33(6): 630-49. Available at: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4926781/>
- 77 Virtanen, Marianna et al. 2013. "Perceived job insecurity as a risk factor for incident coronary heart disease: systematic review and meta-analysis". *BMJ* 347, f4746-f4746. Available at: <https://www.bmj.com/content/347/bmj.f4746>
- 78 Kim, T. J. & von dem Knesebeck, O. 2016. "Perceived job insecurity, unemployment and depressive symptoms: a systematic review and meta-analysis of prospective observational studies." *Int. Arch. Occup. Environ. Health* 89: 561-573. Available at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26715495/>
- 79 Kim, Tae Jun & Olaf von dem Knesebeck. 2015. "Is an insecure job better for health than having no job at all? A systematic review of studies investigating the health-related risks of both job insecurity and unemployment." *BMC Public Health* 15, 985. Available at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26419739/>
- 80 Hsieh, Chang-Tai, Erik Hurst, Charles I. Jones, and Peter J. Klenow. 2019. "The allocation of talent and US economic growth." *Econometrica* 87 (5): 1439-1474. Available at: <http://klenow.com/HHJK.pdf>
- 81 Bell, Alex, Raj Chetty, Xavier Jaravel, Neviana Petkova, and John Van Reenen. 2019. "Who becomes an inventor in America? The importance of exposure to innovation." *The Quarterly Journal of Economics* 134 (2): 647-713. Available at: <https://academic.oup.com/qje/article/134/2/647/5218522>
- 82 Romero, David, Johan Stahre, Thorsten Wuest, Ovidiu Noran, Peter Bernus, Åsa Fast-Berglund, and Dominic Gorecky. 2016. "Towards an operator 4.0 typology: a human-centric perspective on the fourth industrial revolution technologies." In *Proceedings of the international conference on computers and industrial engineering (CIE46), Tianjin, China*, pp. 29-31. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/309609488_Towards_an_Operator_40_Typology_A_Human-Centric_Perspective_on_the_Fourth_Industrial_Revolution_Technologies
- 83 Narayanan, Sriram and Ed Terris. 2020. "Inclusive manufacturing: The impact of disability diversity on productivity in a work integration social enterprise." *Manufacturing & Service Operations Management* 22 (6): 1112-1130.
- 84 Powell, Andy. 2021. "Disabled People in Employment" Research Briefing, House of Commons Library, 1st April. Available at: <https://commonslibrary.parliament.uk/research-briefings/cbp-7540/>
- 85 Boehm, Stephan A., Florian Kunze, and Heike Bruch. 2014. "Spotlight on age-diversity climate: The impact of age-inclusive HR practices on firm-level outcomes." *Personnel Psychology* 67 (3): 667-704. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/259555022_Spotlight_on_Age-Diversity_Climate_The_Impact_of_Age-Inclusive_HR_Practices_on_Firm-Level_Outcomes
- 86 Felstead, Alan, and Golo Henseke. 2017. "Assessing the growth of remote working and its consequences for effort, well-being and work-life balance." *New Technology, Work and Employment* 32 (3): 195-212. Available at: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/ntwe.12097>

Endnotes

- 87 Taylor, Heather, Rebecca Florisson and Liz Spratt. 2021. "Post-pandemic hybrid working poses new challenges to diversity and inclusion" *Work Foundation*. Available at: <https://www.lancaster.ac.uk/work-foundation/news/blog/post-pandemic-hybrid-working-poses-new-challenges-to-diversity-and-inclusion/>
- 88 Gillet, Nicolas, Tiphaine Huyghebaert-Zouaghi, Stéphanie Austin, Claude Fernet, and Alexandre JS Morin. 2021. "Remote working: A double-edged sword for workers' personal and professional well-being." *Journal of Management & Organization* 27 (6): 1060–1082. Available at: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/journal-of-management-and-organization/article/abs/remote-working-a-doubleedged-sword-for-workers-personal-and-professional-wellbeing/33F42F49762DDF609E628FCD6075A12E>
- 89 Etheridge, Ben, Yikai Wang, and Li Tang. 2020. "Worker productivity during lockdown and working from home: Evidence from self-reports". No. 2020-12. *ISER Working Paper Series*. Available at: <https://www.iser.essex.ac.uk/research/publications/working-papers/iser/2020-12>
- 90 O'Neil, Cathy. 2016. *Weapons of math destruction: How big data increases inequality and threatens democracy*. London: Penguin.
- 91 Brussevich, Mariya, Ms Era Dabla-Norris, and Salma Khalid. 2019. "Is technology widening the gender gap? Automation and the future of female employment". *International Monetary Fund*. Available at: <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/WP/Issues/2019/05/06/Is-Technology-Widening-the-Gender-Gap-Automation-and-the-Future-of-Female-Employment-46684>
- 92 Kandera, Karlis, Jyldyz Djumalieva, Cath Sleeman, and Jack Orlik. 2020. "Mapping career causeways: supporting workers at risk." *Nesta*. Available at: https://media.nesta.org.uk/documents/Mapping_Career_Causeways_01_G2XA7SL.pdf
- 93 Rosenblat, Alex, Karen EC Levy, Solon Barocas, and Tim Hwang. 2017. "Discriminating tastes: Uber's customer ratings as vehicles for workplace discrimination." *Policy & Internet* 9(2017): 256–279. Available at: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/poi3.153>
- 94 Binns, Reuben Abigail Gilbert, Anne-Marie Imafidon, Tim Johnston, David Leslie, Joshua Simons, Logan Graham, Anna Thomas. 2020. "Mind the Gap: How to fill the equality and AI gap in an automated world". *Institute for the Future of Work*. Available at: <https://www.ifow.org/publications/mind-the-gap-the-final-report-of-the-equality-task-force>
- 95 For instance, the use of certain language or emoji's on social media profiles.
- 96 Centre for Data Ethics and Innovation. 2020. "Review into bias in algorithmic decision-making". Available at: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/957259/Review_into_bias_in_algorithmic_decision-making.pdf
- 97 Graham, Logan, Abigail Gilbert, Joshua Simons, Anna Thomas. 2020. "Artificial intelligence in hiring: Assessing impacts on equality". *Institute for the Future of Work*. Available at: <https://www.ifow.org/publications/artificial-intelligence-in-hiring-assessing-impacts-on-equality>
- 98 Sheir, Stephanie, Dora Meredith, Abigail Gilbert, Anna Thomas. 2021. "Algorithmic impact assessments: Building a systematic framework of accountability for algorithmic decision making" *Institute for the Future of Work*. Available at: <https://www.ifow.org/publications/policy-briefing-building-a-systematic-framework-of-accountability-for-algorithmic-decision-making>
- 99 Latemore, Greg. 2017. "Dignity and Leadership: Implications of Leaders' Language and Their Assumptions of Human Nature", in *Dignity and the Organization*, ed. Monika Kostera and Michael Pireson, 149–171. Available at: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1057/978-1-137-55562-5_8
- 100 Leslie, David, Christopher Burr, Mhairi Aitken, Josh Cows, Mike Katell and Morgan Briggs. 2021. "Artificial intelligence, human rights, democracy, and the rule of law: a primer." Alan Turing Institute. Available at: https://www.turing.ac.uk/sites/default/files/2021-03/cahai_feasibility_study_primer_final.pdf
- 101 Binns, Reuben, Abigail Gilbert, Anne-Marie Imafidon, Tim Johnston, Joshua Simons, Logan Graham, Anna Thomas. 2020. "Mind the Gap: How to fill the Equality and Accountability Gap In an Automated World" *Institute for the Future of Work*. Available at: <https://www.ifow.org/publications/mind-the-gap-the-final-report-of-the-equality-task-force>
- 102 Sayer, Andrew. 2007. "Dignity at work: Broadening the agenda." *Organization* 14 (4): 565–581.
- 103 Gilbert, Abigail and Anna Thomas. 2021. "An Amazonian Era: The Gigification of Work". *Institute for the Future of Work*. Available at: <https://www.ifow.org/publications/the-amazonian-era-the-gigification-of-work>
- 104 Marks, Abigail, Lila Skountridaki, and Oliver Mallett. 2020. "Don't say goodbye to Zoom yet: most people want to get back to the office, but not for the full week." *The Conversation*. Available at: <https://theconversation.com/dont-say-goodbye-to-zoom-yet-most-people-want-to-get-back-to-the-office-but-not-for-the-full-week-151057>
- 105 Gilbert, Abigail and Anna Thomas. 2021. "An Amazonian Era: The Gigification of Work". *Institute for the Future of Work*. Available at: <https://www.ifow.org/publications/the-amazonian-era-the-gigification-of-work>
- 106 O'Neil, L. 2021. "Amazon's denial of workers urinating in bottles puts the pee in PR fiasco" *The Guardian*. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/lifeandstyle/2021/mar/25/amazon-bottles-pee-tweet-warehouse-workers>
- 107 Lohr, Steve. 2018. "Facial recognition is accurate, if you're a white guy." *New York Times*. Available at: <https://www.nytimes.com/2018/02/09/technology/facial-recognition-race-artificial-intelligence.html>

Endnotes

- 108 Van der Sloot, Bart. 2015. "Privacy as Personality Right: Why the ECtHR's Focus on Ulterior Interests Might Prove Indispensable in the Age of Big Data." *Utrecht Journal of International & European Law*. 31(25). Available at: <https://utrechtjournal.org/articles/10.5334/ujiel.cp/>
- 109 Van der Sloot, Bart. 2015.
- 110 Council of Europe. "CAHAI - Ad hoc Committee on Artificial Intelligence" Available at: <https://www.coe.int/en/web/artificial-intelligence/cahai>
- 111 Felten, E.W., M. Raj, and R. Seamans. 2018., "A Method to Link Advances in Artificial Intelligence to Occupational Abilities". *AEA Papers and Proceedings*, 2018. 108: p. 54–57.
- 112 Gambardella, Alfonso, Pooyan Khashabi, and Claudio Panico. 2019. "Managing Autonomy in Industrial R&D: A Project-Level Investigation." *Organization Science*, forthcoming.
- 113 Kruse, D., J. Blasi, and R. Freeman, Does linking worker pay to firm performance help the best firms do even better? NBER Working Paper 17745, 2012. 53: p. 30.
- 114 Lampel, J., A. Banerjee, and A. Bhalla. 2017. "The Ownership Effect Inquiry: What Does the Evidence Tell Us?" Available at: http://theownershipeffect.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/The_Ownership_Effect-Inquiry_Final_Evidence_Report.pdf; Park, R., D. Kruse, and J. Sesil, Does Employee Ownership Enhance Firm Survival? *Advances in the Economic Analysis of Participatory and Labor-Managed Firms*, 2004. 8: p. 3–33; Freeman, S.F., *Effects of ESOP Adoption and Employee Ownership: Thirty years of Research and Experience Part of the Organizational Behavior and Theory Commons*. 2007; Kurtulus, F.A. and D.L. Kruse, *How Did Employee Ownership Firms Weather the Last Two Recessions?: Employee Ownership, Employment Stability, and Firm Survival: 1999–2011*. 2017.
- 115 Park, R., D. Kruse, and J. Sesil. 2004. "Does Employee Ownership Enhance Firm Survival? *Advances in the Economic Analysis of Participatory and Labor-Managed Firms*" 8: 3–33. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/235263725_Does_employee_ownership_enhance_firm_survival
- 116 Gilbert, Abigail and Anna Thomas. 2021. "An Amazonian Era: How Algorithmic Systems Erode Good Work". *Institute for the Future of Work*. Available at: <https://www.ifow.org/publications/the-amazonian-era-the-gigification-of-work>
- 117 Bipp, Tanja, Maren Oberländer, and Marvin Walczok. 2021. "The dark side of autonomy: The role of autonomy facets and work intensification." In *Academy of Management Proceedings*. Briarcliff Manor, NY 10510: Academy of Management. Available at: <https://journals.aom.org/doi/abs/10.5465/AMBPP.2021.11153abstract>
- 118 Petrakaki, Dimitra, and Andreas Kornelakis. 2016. "'We can only request what's in our protocol': technology and work autonomy in healthcare." *New Technology, Work and Employment* 31 (3): 223–237. Available at: <http://srodev.sussex.ac.uk/id/eprint/64107/1/Author%27s%20accepted%20version.pdf>
- 119 Calvo, Rafael A., Dorian Peters, Karina Vold, and Richard M. Ryan. 2020. "Supporting human autonomy in AI systems: A framework for ethical enquiry." In *Ethics of Digital Well-Being*, pp. 31–54. Springer, Cham. Available at: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-50585-1_2
- 120 Solon, A. 2018. "Amazon patented a wristband to guide workers hands to the correct shelves" *The Guardian*. Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2018/jan/31/amazon-warehouse-wristband-tracking>
- 121 Fatigue Monitoring Systems come in the form of wearable smart hats and caps, watches and fitbits, or facial monitoring systems which can be from cameras in screens or the workplace. Such systems are increasingly commonplace across in-situ and desk-based work contexts.
- 122 Green, Francis. 2000. "Why has work effort become more intense? Conjectures and evidence about effort-biased technical change and other stories." *Studies in Economics* No. 0003. School of Economics, University of Kent. Available at: <https://ideas.repec.org/p/ukc/ukcedp/0003.html>
- 123 Siegrist, Johannes. 2016. "Effort-reward imbalance model." In *Stress: Concepts, cognition, emotion, and behavior*, pp. 81–86. Academic Press; Kinman, Gail, and Fiona Jones. 2008. "Effort-reward imbalance, over-commitment and work-life conflict: testing an expanded model." *Journal of Managerial Psychology*. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/200824398_Effort-reward_imbalance_over-commitment_and_work-life_conflict_Testing_an_expanded_model
- 124 Schildt, Henri. 2020. *The data imperative: How digitalization is reshaping management, organizing, and work.* Oxford University Press.
- 125 Yeung, Karen. 2017. "'Hypernudge': Big Data as a mode of regulation by design." *Information, Communication & Society* 20 (1): 118–136. Available at: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/1369118X.2016.1186713>
- 126 Pissarides, Chris and Anna Thomas "Good Work: The Foundation of a Moral Economy" *Institute for the Future of Work*. Available at: <https://www.ifow.org/publications/the-future-of-good-work-the-foundation-of-a-modern-moral-economy>
- 127 Institute for the Future of Work. 2021. Good Work Monitor. Available at: <https://www.ifow.org/resources/the-good-work-monitor>

Endnotes

- 128 Clausen, Thomas, Line Rosendahl Meldgaard Pedersen, Malene Friis Andersen, Tores Theorell, and Ida EH Madsen. 2021. "Job autonomy and psychological well-being: A linear or a non-linear association?" *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*. Available at: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/1359432X.2021.1972973>
- 129 Faragher, E.B., *The relationship between job satisfaction and health: a meta-analysis*. Occupational and Environmental Medicine, 2005. 62(2): p. 105-112; Böckerman, P.; Ilmakunnas, P. 2010. "The job satisfaction-productivity nexus: A study using matched survey and register data." *Ind. Labor Relat. Rev.* 65: 244–262. Available at: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/001979391206500203>
- 130 Zelenski, J.M.; Murphy, S.A.; Jenkins, D.A. 2008. "The happy-productive worker thesis revisited." *Journal of Happiness Studies*. 9: 521–537. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/23545643_The_Happy-Productive_Worker_Thesis_Revisited
- 131 Isham, Amy, Simon Mair, and Tim Jackson. 2021 "Worker wellbeing and productivity in advanced economies: Re-examining the link." *Ecological Economics* 184: 106989. Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0921800921000471>
- 132 Sehnbruch, Kirsten. 2004. "From the quantity to the quality of employment: An application of the Capability Approach to the Chilean labour market." *Center for Latin American Studies*. Available at: <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/1ff3s1c6>
- 133 Day, Arla, Ryan Cook, Rachael Jones-Chick, and Vanessa Myers. 2021. "Are your smart technologies killing it or killing you? Developing a research agenda for workplace ICT and worker wellbeing." In *A Research Agenda for Workplace Stress and Wellbeing*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- 134 Gilbert, Abigail and Anna Thomas. 2021. "An Amazonian Era: The Gigification of Work" *Institute for the Future of Work*. Available at: <https://www.ifow.org/publications/the-amazonian-era-the-gigification-of-work>
- 135 Newman, Nathan. 2017. "Reengineering workplace bargaining: how big data drives lower wages and how reframing labor law can restore information equality in the workplace." *U. Cin. L. Rev.* 85: 693. Available at: <https://heinonline.org/HOL/LandingPage?handle=hein.journals/ucinlr85&div=32&id=&page=>
- 136 Chesley, Noelle. 2014. "Information and communication technology use, work intensification and employee strain and distress." *Work, employment and society* 28 (4): 589–610. Available at: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/0950017013500112>
- 137 Ball, Kirstie. 2021. "Electronic Monitoring and Surveillance in the Workplace". No. JRC125716. *Joint Research Centre*. Available at: <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC125716>
- 138 Molino, Monica, Emanuela Ingusci, Fulvio Signore, Amelia Manuti, Maria Luisa Giancaspro, Vincenzo Russo, Margherita Zito, and Claudio G. Cortese. 2020. "Wellbeing costs of technology use during Covid-19 remote working: An investigation using the Italian translation of the technostress creators scale." *Sustainability* 12 (15): 5911. Available at: <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/12/15/5911>
- 139 Bordi, Laura, Jussi Okkonen, Jaana-Piia Mäkineniemi, and Kirsi Heikkilä-Tammi. 2018. "Communication in the digital work environment: implications for wellbeing at work." *Nordic Journal of Working Life Studies*. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/324477041_Communication_in_the_Digital_Work_Environment_Implications_for_Wellbeing_at_Work
- 140 Adams, Jerome M. 2019. "The value of worker well-being." *Public Health Reports* 134 (6): 583–586.
- 141 Warhust, Chris and Derek Bosworth. 2020. "Does Good Work Have a Positive Effect on Productivity? Developing the Evidence Base." In *Can Good Work Solve the Productivity Puzzle?*
- 142 Macduffie, J.P. 1995. "Human Resource Bundles and Manufacturing Performance: Organizational Logic and Flexible Production Systems in the World Auto Industry." *Industrial and Labor Relations Review*. 48: 197. Available at: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/001979399504800201>
- 143 Bartel, A.P., C. Ichniowski, and K.L. Shaw. 2005. "How does information technology really affect productivity? Plant-level comparisons of product innovation, process improvement and worker skills." NBER Working Paper Series. Available at: <https://www.nber.org/papers/w11773>
- 144 Zwick, T. 2006. "The impact of training intensity on establishment productivity." *Industrial Relations*. 45: 26–46; Ichniowski, C., K. Shaw, and G. Prennushi, *The effects of Human Resource Management practices on productivity*, in *NBER Working Paper Series*. 1995.
- 145 Chiaburu, D.S., K. Van Dam, and H.M. Hutchins. 2010. "Social support in the workplace and training transfer: A longitudinal analysis." *International Journal of Selection and Assessment*. 18: 187–200. Available at: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/j.1468-2389.2010.00500.x>
- 146 Tera Allas CBE, McKinsey and Co 'From Trade Offs to Win-Wins: How We Can Unlock Productivity and Good Jobs' in 'Can Good Work Solve the Productivity Puzzle'
- 147 Brown, Ron. 2018. "Robots, New Technology, and Industry 4.0 in Changing Workplaces. Impacts on Labor and Employment Laws." *Am. U. Bus. L. Rev.* 7: 349. Available at: <https://digitalcommons.wcl.american.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1109&context=aubl>

Endnotes

- 148 Community and the Institute for the Future of Work. 2021. "Technology Agreements: A Partnership Approach to Use of Technology at Work" *Community Union*. Available at: https://20t4kl3bmt1vfknwx15oqye8-wpengine.netdna-ssl.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/RGB_A_partnership_Approach_to_Use_of_Technology_at_Work_Oct21.pdf
- 149 The TUC suggests worker tech and the collection of workplace data could be the basis of a new role for unions, and level the playing field in terms of the way analytics shape negotiation.
- 150 Kumar, S., Calvo, R., Avendano, M., Sivaramakrishnan, K. & Berkman, L. F. 2012. "Social support, volunteering and health around the world: Cross-national evidence from 139 countries". *Soc. Sci. Med.* 74: 696–706. Available at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/22305947/>
- 151 Scarlet, Valentin. 2009. "Employment and Social Cohesion." MPRA Paper 19983. University Library of Munich, Germany. Available at: <https://ideas.repec.org/p/pramprapa/19983.html>
- 152 Gilbert, Abigail and Anna Thomas. 2021. "The Amazonian Era: The Gigification of Work" *Institute for the Future of Work*. Available at: <https://www.ifow.org/publications/the-amazonian-era-the-gigification-of-work>
- 153 Palmer, Annie. 2020. "How Amazon keeps a close eye on employee activism to head off unions" *CNBC* 24 October 2020. Available at: <https://www.cnn.com/2020/10/24/how-amazon-prevents-unions-by-surveilling-employee-activism.html>
- 154 Stretfield, David. 2021. "How Amazon Crushes Unions" *New York Times*. Available at: <https://www.nytimes.com/2021/03/16/technology/amazon-unions-virginia.html>
- 155 Department for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy. 2021. "The use of public engagement for technological innovation, Literature review and case studies" Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/the-use-of-public-engagement-for-technological-innovation-literature-review-and-case-studies>
- 156 Arthur, J.B. 1994. "Effects of Human Resource Systems on Manufacturing Performance and Turnover". *Academy of Management Journal*. 37: 670–687. Available at: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/256705?seq=1>;
- Macduffie, J.P. 1995. "Human Resource Bundles and Manufacturing Performance: Organizational Logic and Flexible Production Systems in the World Auto Industry". *Industrial and Labor Relations Review*. 48: 197;
- Vandenberg, R.J., H.A. Richardson, and L.J. Eastman. 1999. "The Impact of High Involvement Work Processes on Organizational Effectiveness: A Second-Order Latent Variable Approach". *Group and Organization Management*. 24: 300–339;
- Hoque, K. 1999. "Human Resource Management and Performance in the UK Hotel Industry". 37: 419–443;
- Doucouliaagos, C. 1995. "Worker Participation and Productivity in Labor-Managed and Participatory Capitalist Firms: A Meta-Analysis". *Industrial and Labor Relations Review* 49: 58. Available at: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/001979399504900104>
- 157 Doucouliagos, C. 1995. "Worker Participation and Productivity in Labor-Managed and Participatory Capitalist Firms: A Meta-Analysis". *Industrial and Labor Relations Review*. 49: 58. Available at: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/001979399504900104>
- 158 Warhust, Chris and Derek Bosworth. 2020. "Does Good Work Have a Positive Effect on Productivity? Developing the Evidence Base". In 'Can Good Work Solve the Productivity Puzzle'
- 159 Kontoghiorghes, C. 2001. "Factors Affecting Training Effectiveness in the Context of the Introduction of New Technology—A US Case Study". *International Journal of Training and Development*. 5: 248–260. Available at: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/1468-2419.00137>
- 160 Trist, E.L. and K.W. Bamforth. 1951. "Some Social and Psychological Consequences of the Longwall Method of Coal-Getting: An Examination of the Psychological Situation and Defences of a Work Group in Relation to the Social Structure and Technological Content of the Work System". *Human Relations*. 4: 3–38. Available at: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/001872675100400101>
- 161 McQuaid, R., et al. 2012. "Fit for work? Health and Wellbeing of Employees in Employee Owned Business". *Employee Ownership Association*. Available at: <https://employeeownership.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/Fit-for-Work.pdf>
- 162 Binns, Reuben Abigail Gilbert, Anne-Marie Imafidon, Tim Johnston, David Leslie, Joshua Simons, Logan Graham, Anna Thomas. 2020. "Mind the Gap: How to fill the equality and AI gap in an automated world" *Institute for the Future of Work*. Available at: <https://www.ifow.org/publications/mind-the-gap-the-final-report-of-the-equality-task-force>
- 163 Dobbe, Roel, Thomas Krendl Gilbert, and Yonatan Mintz. 2019. "Hard choices in artificial intelligence: Addressing normative uncertainty through sociotechnical commitments." *AIES '20: Proceedings of the AAAI/ACM Conference on AI, Ethics, and Society*. Available at: <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3375627.3375861>
- 164 Gilbert, Abigail and Anna Thomas. 2021. "An Amazonian Era: The gigification of work". *Institute for the Future of Work*. Available at: <https://www.ifow.org/publications/the-amazonian-era-the-gigification-of-work>
- 165 Pöttsch, Holger, and Kerem Schamberger. 2022. "Labour Struggles in Digital Capitalism: Challenges and Opportunities for Worker Organisation, Mobilisation, and Activism in Germany." *Journal for a Global Sustainable Information Society* 20 (1): 82-100. Available at: <https://www.triple-c.at/index.php/tripleC/article/view/1314>
- 166 Birhane, Abeba, Pratyusha Kalluri, Dallas Card, William Agnew, Ravit Dotan, and Michelle Bao. 2021. "The values encoded in machine learning research." Available at: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2106.15590>
- 167 Dobbe, Roel, Thomas Krendl Gilbert, and Yonatan Mintz. 2019.

Endnotes

- 168 Please note: The productivity benefits of training are likely to be contingent upon numerous local factors, ranging from product market to labour relations, to sectoral characteristics, and national institutional contexts [20, 25, 30].
- 169 Smit et al. 2020. McKinsey report – citing Society for Human Resource Management, Human capital benchmarking report, November 2016.
- 170 Dearden, Lorraine, Howard Reed and John Van Reenen. 2006. “The impact of training on productivity and wages: evidence from British panel data”. *The Institute for Fiscal Studies*. Available at: <https://ifs.org.uk/wps/wp0516.pdf>
- 171 Zwick, T. 2006. “The impact of training intensity on establishment productivity”. *Industrial Relations*. 45: 26–46. Available at: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/j.1468-232X.2006.00412.x>
- 172 Dearden, Lorraine, Howard Reed and John Van Reenen. 2006. “The impact of training on productivity and wages: evidence from British panel data”. *The Institute for Fiscal Studies*. Available at: <https://ifs.org.uk/wps/wp0516.pdf>
- 173 Schmidt, Steven W. 2007. “The Relationship Between Satisfaction with Workplace Training and Overall Job Satisfaction”. *Human Resource Development Quarterly*. 18(4): 481–498. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/227657996_The_Relationship_between_Satisfaction_with_Workplace_Training_and_Overall_Job_Satisfaction
- 174 Memon, Mumtaz A., Rohani Salleh, and Mohamed Noor Rosli Baharom. 2016. “The link between training satisfaction, work engagement and turnover intention.” *European Journal of Training and Development*. 40(6): 407–429. Available at: <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/EJTD-10-2015-0077/full/html>
- 175 Surcher, Sandra J. and Shalene Gupta. 2018. “A Better, Fairer Approach to Layoffs.” *Harvard Business Review*. Available at: <https://hbr.org/2018/05/layoffs-that-dont-break-your-company>
- 176 Reques, Laura, Carolina Giráldez-García, Estrella Miqueleiz, Maria. J. Belza and Enrique Regidor. 2014. “Educational differences in mortality and the relative importance of different causes of death: a 7-year follow-up study of Spanish adults”. *Journal of Epidemiology and Community Health* 68(12): 1151–60. Available at: <https://jech.bmj.com/content/68/12/1151>
- 177 Oshio, Takashi. 2018. “Widening disparities in health between educational levels and their determinants in later life: evidence from a nine-year cohort study”. *BMC Public Health* 18, 278. Available at: <https://bmcpublichealth.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12889-018-5181-7>
- 178 Hughes, Deirdre and Karen Adriaanse. 2017. “Adult Education: Important for health and well-being”. *Warwick Institute for Employment Research*. Available at: https://warwick.ac.uk/fac/soc/ier/research/adult_education/adult_education_ier_report_final_2401018.pdf
- 179 Ekbia, Hamid, and Bonnie Nardi. 2014. “Heteromation and its (dis) contents: The invisible division of labor between humans and machines.” *First Monday*. Available at: <https://firstmonday.org/article/view/5331/4090>
- 180 This is important in the context of a lack of investment – of the 1.5million in jobs most vulnerable to automation, 99% do not have higher education degrees.
- 181 Li, Jiaqi, Anna Valero, Guglielmo Ventura. 2020. “Trends in job-related training and policies for building future skills into the recovery”. *Centre for Vocational Educational Research*. Available at: <https://cver.lse.ac.uk/textonly/cver/pubs/cverdp033.pdf>
- 182 Bubonya, Melisa, Deborah A. Cobb-Clark, and Mark Wooden. 2014. “A family affair: job loss and the mental health of spouses and adolescents.” *Institute for the Study of Labor*. Available at: <https://www.econstor.eu/handle/10419/106530>
- 183 Brand, Jennie E. 2015. “The far-reaching impact of job loss and unemployment.” *Annual Review of Sociology* 41: 359–375. Available at: <https://www.annualreviews.org/doi/abs/10.1146/annurev-soc-071913-043237>
- 184 Tcherneva, Pavlina R. 2017. “Unemployment: The silent epidemic.” *Levy Economics Institute*, Working Papers Series 895. Available at: https://www.levyinstitute.org/pubs/wp_895.pdf
- 185 McLellan, Robert K. 2017. “Work, health, and worker well-being: roles and opportunities for employers.” *Health Affairs* 36(2): 206–213. Available at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/28167707/>

Somerset House
The Exchange
London
WC2R 1LA

www.ifow.org
[@FutureWorkInst](https://twitter.com/FutureWorkInst)